

Employee Perceptions on Human Resource Management Practices in the Banking Sector in Telangana.

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Abstract:

Human resources seem to be the most important assets for every institution 's success. The financial sector will be unable to meet its commitments except their personnel are retrained in modern perspectives and expertise. The banking sector in India have witnessed a transition from traditional banking to technology driven banking. Employee's perception can affect organizational productivity positively when they are willing and committed to organizational goals. When employee's perceptions are considered, staff absenteeism is reduced, there's greater organizational commitment, improved performance, reduced turnover and greater job satisfaction. The purpose of this paper is to find out the perception of employees towards human resource management practices in banking sector in Telangana. A systematic questionnaire was constructed utilising a 5-point Likert scale and administered to 300 participants that are employed in major commercial banks in Telangana. The research uncovered that bank employees have positive perception towards human resource management practices and banking sector's HR managers will benefit greatly from this research, as it precisely illustrates that beneficial contributions can be gained from personnel who have positive perception towards organisationand hrm practices.

Keywords: Perception, HRM Practices, Banking sector, Productivity.

1. Introduction:

Employee perception is the mechanism through which people organise and analyse their physiological input in attempt to make sense of their surroundings and vital in interpreting human way of behaving in light of the fact that each individual sees the world and address life challenges in an unexpected way (Kooij, D. T., & Boon, C. (2018). According to studies, the way individuals view their workplace environment has the greatest impact on their output. As a result, managers must measure or evaluate how employees feel about their occupations in order to impact performance (Hewett, R., Shantz, A., & Mundy, J. (2019). Perception is vital

for the supervisor who needs to abstain from making blunders while managing individuals and occasions at the workplace. This issue is worse by the way that various individuals see what is happening in an unexpected way. Supervisors must have a thorough understanding of their employees' perceptions in attempt to handle them adequately (Sumelius, J., Björkman, I., Ehrnrooth, M., Mäkelä, K., & Smale, A. (2014). Individuals who have a favourable attitude toward their supervisor, their job, and their connections inside the organization are more likely to be effective and continue with the organization for a long period. Talented personnel may seek possibilities somewhere if they have adverse impressions of the organisation and the workplace as per Dr. Naveen Prasadula. HRM is described simply a set of rules, procedures and techniques that govern the attitudes, perception, and efficiency of personnel and focusing on the HRM is a significant prerequisite for each association. HRM methodologies must be appropriate in direction to gain the strategic edge and create an atmosphere conducive to accomplishing the organization's goals (Yamamoto, H. (2013). Any strategy that concerns to boost capabilities, engagement, dedication, and strategic leadership within an organisation can be defined as human resource management approach. Appropriate human resource management strategies create a huge difference in organisation functioning. Such strategies must be recognised within the organisation and executed in an economical way and to be continually monitored and modified in order to ensure its efficacy and suitability (Ramakrishna, P., & Srinivasa, K. (2017). Personnel perception assumes a critical part and generally decides achievement and disappointment of an organization. In most organisations, employee perceptions concerning task and enterprise human resource strategies assume a significant role (Bednall, T. C., Sanders, K., & Runhaar, P. (2014). Personnel perceptions towards organisation and HR practises will be shaped by the institution's workplace environment. Various studies revealed that, the way personnel view their workplace environment has significant impact on actual performance. As a result, managers must measure how employees feel about their positions in order to impact performance

2. Importance of Perception at Workplace:

If a supervisor wishes to be impactful and avert blunders at the workplace, he must first perceive his subordinates' perspectives. It would guide supervisors in anticipating workforce conduct because he will be acquainted of their perspectives (Dumont, J., Shen, J., & Deng, X. (2017). When confronted with the same scenario, various people act in various ways or diversely because they see the circumstances differentially. An individual's way of behaving can be anticipated by getting what is going on and his present impression of the surroundings (Fletcher, L., Alfes, K., & Robinson, D. (2018). Workplace friction can result in a range of issues, including decreased efficiency, distrust between peers, and sometimes even greater absenteeism and attrition. To minimise such issues, supervisors should concentrate on

perception-checking, which can guide executives to eliminate misconceptions and foster successful workplace interactions (Kehoe, R. R., & Wright, P. M. (2013). Perception-checking will raise staff enthusiasm by recognising that the organisation focusing on what they are talking about and it offers them a chance to explain their viewpoints, concepts, or recommendations, if managers did not completely comprehend what they were talking about (Herrbach, O., Mignonac, K., Vandenberghe, C., & Negrini, A. (2019). How well the supervisor interacts with staff, the structure of the operational environment, corporation's norms and practices in particular, and how much faith and regard exists among supervisors, staff members and colleagues are all aspects that might influence perceptions of employees (Redmond, E. (2013).

3. Perceptual Barriers: The most common perceptual barriers are as follows:

- i) Selective Perception:** Selective perception entails focusing on details which matches your beliefs while dismissing the remaining. If individuals distrust their supervisor, then they are more likely to concentrate on their bad traits and overlook any favourable attributes that contradict your perception of them (Li, X., & Frenkel, S. (2017).
- ii) Halo Effect:** At the point when an individual sees someone else in a positive manner paying little heed to their actions. When supervisors deliver unduly positive assessments of individuals solely on isolated achievements, the halo effect arises. Managers frequently make the halo mistake of assuming that someone with a solid participation track is competent for all aspects of effectiveness (Piening, E. P., Baluch, A. M., & Salge, T. O. (2013).
- iii) Projection:** It is the propensity to ascribe one's own convictions, sentiments, attitude, intentions, or desires to others. A chief who appreciates taking on new obligations might extend this propensity on to individuals by allotting them additional work obligations without discussing with employees beforehand. Or when an individual loves to discuss on sensitive issues, they may expect that other will perform as same and as a consequence, indulge into confidential concepts before thinking over whether or not it may cause specific individuals awkward
- iv) Expectations:** It is the willingness to discover whatever one tries to see in a circumstance or in an individual. These predictions have a significant influence over how individuals experience the environment. Whenever people inquire about someone's well-being, and anticipate that they should respond, "Great, or probably ok". People may opt to overlook non - verbal communication when someone's reply is backed by poor bodily posture since it contradicts our preconceptions (Frenkel, S. J., Restubog, S. L. D., & Bednall, T. (2012).
- v) Stereotype:** It is a generalised psychological image which is connected with a specific population. If a supervisor perceives that new recruit are sluggish and observe that few of

the younger employees are continuing to take longer pauses, however forget to observe that the senior employees are performing likewise.

4. Overcome Perceptual Barriers:

Although perceptual obstacles may be deep-seated, identifying and addressing these obstacles is not difficult. It is vital to conquer these hindrances to promote pleasant relationships and mindsets and take on uplifting outlooks toward people. This fortifies relational connections as well as further develops working environment culture (Acharya, B. B., & Swain, H. K. (2016). Fostering efficient workplace correspondence promotes a healthy working culture, boosts efficiency, facilitates mutual understanding, and trains employees to listen to individuals' perspectives with a positive mindset (Solberg, E., & Dysvik, A. (2016). While listening, do not draw any conclusions regarding the content being presented and listen carefully and share the suggestions or criticism afterwards (Bednall, T. C., Sanders, K., & Runhaar, P. (2014).

5. Review of Literature:

Kavitha, S. F. (2017) personnel perceptions are shaped by organisational responsibilities, team cohesion, and interpersonal communication layouts, among other factors, thus it is critical for the organisation to frame the appropriate perception in the personalities of its personnel. The study revealed that 39% of participants agree that firm has a decent workplace environment, while 11% believe their organisation has an outstanding workplace culture. S. Iqbal (2016) employee's perceived that in today's fast-paced corporate world, hiring processes must be prioritised. Individual's confidence to participate and promote their talents and knowledge may be boosted by impartial hiring and screening practices. This could aid in the acquisition of innovative ideas, which will ultimately strengthen the expertise capabilities of the company. Bhatt, P. (2016) The area of human resource management is evolving much quickly nowadays than previously because of modifications in the paradigm of the worldwide financial climate of industry. The human resource practices are once again recognized as the greatest significant component of all the organizational variables that leads to organizational success.

Suman, J., Sharma, S., et. al. (2012) suggested that employee's perceived that participation programs are decided and lawfully implemented in nationalized banks. Furthermore, to preserve an amicable working arrangement to nationalized banks, the retirement, insurance, gratuity was effectively enforced. Chakrabarty, K. C. (2012) respondents perceived that progressive change is required in human resource management practices in banks to survive in dynamic environment. It is necessary to create a database of dedicated employees for the succeeding and continued growth of banks, by making employees aware of their requirements and desires and by ensuring that employees are happy to work. They would

benefit from their success and dedication, which eventually would affect banks growth and profitability. Zulfqar Bowra and Kabir Niazi (2011) in their research paper “Impact of human resource practices on employee perceived performance in banking sector of Pakistan” It was discovered that human resource activities and individual perceived efficiency have a favourable and substantial connection, and it is critical for institutions to realise that their human resource policies influence individual efficiency, which affects the institution’s overall success. Several researchers have identified a variety of human resource organisational strategies which have a tremendous impact on productivity. Bos-Nehles, A. C., & Veenendaal, A. A. (2019) Employee viewpoints are driven mostly by benefits supplied by their employer, which influences employee perceptions, according to the researcher. Happiness, usefulness or relevance and the apparent purpose of the organisation in giving the financial reward to individuals are key aspects that seems to impact personnel perceptions. Notwithstanding, it has been argued that several perks are viewed as obligations or privileges that the company provides to its workforce. Reward realization, and the institution's apparent motivation for giving a reward were proven to have a direct correlation with individual perceptions.

Dello Russo, S., Mascia, D., et al. (2018) expressed that bank establishments are the foundation or spine of a country's economy growth. Productive administration of HR and preservation of optimised workforce consistent engagement have an impact on the economy's overall prosperity and productivity. The productive workforce will be better used if they are happy with their positions. This demonstrates that how organizations handle their workforce and satisfy their necessities and aspirations has a significant effect on their perception toward their positions which thus affect the potential or capability of individuals to complete their task productively. Elorza, U., Harris, C., et al. (2016) Work happiness is becoming more fundamental in present dynamic scenario and personnel fulfilment has become a challenging issue for banking institutions. Individuals are continuously faced with unexpected difficulties and possibilities. Modernization, expanding markets, and advanced future technologies are all fostering continuous transformation. Individuals' perspectives or perceptions of their work are shifting as a result of these transformations. Individuals are extremely crucial for any organization's survival in this cut throat competition and motivation, loyalty, participation and retention of individuals are the most valuable assets for banking institutions.

6. Objective of Study:

The objectives of present study are as follows:

- i) To study the HRM practices in publicly-owned and privately-owned sector banks in Telangana.

- ii) To find out the perception of employees towards HRM practices in publicly-owned and privately-owned sector banks in Telangana.
- iii) To contrast the HRM practices in publicly-owned and privately-owned sector banks in Telangana.

7. Hypotheses:

The underlying null hypotheses were constructed to be investigated in study, bearing in mind the research's aims:

Ho (1): In perspective of recruitment and selection criteria, there is no critical difference among publicly-owned and privately-owned segment banks.

Ho (2): In perspective of promotion criteria, there is no critical difference among publicly-owned and privately-owned segment banks.

Ho (3): In perspective of employee participation criteria, there is no critical difference among publicly-owned and privately-owned segment banks.

Ho (4): In perspective of communication criteria, there is no critical difference among publicly-owned and privately-owned segment banks.

Ho (5): In perspective of talent management criteria, there is no critical difference among publicly-owned and privately-owned segment banks

8. Research Methodology:

The study is descriptive and analytical study carried out to find out the perception of employees towards HRM practices based on primary and secondary data. The original or fundamental data was obtained by self-designed questionnaire on 300 bank employees (150 each) from the government owned (Bank of Baroda, Punjab National bank, State bank of India) and privately owned (Icici, Axis, Hdfc Bank) commercial banks in Kurukshetra, Karnal, Kaithal, Ambala and Yamunanagar cities of Telangana. Auxiliary information was accumulated straightly from assorted optional outlets like quarterly statements of Commercial institutions, correlated literature, papers, documents, scholarly articles, official records, websites, blogs, statistical records and academic research etc. Statistical tools like analysis of variance, 't' test have been employed.

9. Data Analysis:

9.1 Reliability Statistics:

Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
0.985	23

For dataset acceptability, Cronbach 's alpha coefficient ought to be higher than 0.7 and in the present study Cronbach's alpha is .985. Therefore, data is reliable for analysis.

9.2 Recruitment and Selection practices perceived by public sector and private sector banks employees:

Recruitment and Selection practices	Banks	N	$\bar{x}$	Σ	$\sigma_{\bar{x}}$	t	p value
Prior to making a choice, the Bank follows a systematic screening procedure.	Public Sector	150	4.3067	.85880	.07012	1.045	0.297
	Private Sector	150	4.1867	1.11359	.09012		
Bank recruits' personnel without discrimination	Public Sector	150	4.1267	1.08248	.08838	1.291	0.198
	Private Sector	150	3.9667	1.06448	.08691		
Bank selects employees primarily focused on competence	Public Sector	150	4.2467	.96889	.07911	1.693	0.091
	Private Sector	150	4.0533	1.00860	.08235		
Bank adopts both internal and external method of recruitment	Public Sector	150	4.4133	.59287	.04841	1.505	0.133
	Private Sector	150	4.3133	.55728	.04550		
The bank conduct fair examination and personal interview for selecting the employees	Public Sector	150	4.2400	.99448	.08120	.860	0.391
	Private Sector	150	4.1200	1.38990	.11348		
Appropriate to conclude that you are satisfied with recruitment policies continued in your Bank	Public Sector	150	4.2000	.79427	.06485	.548	0.584
	Private Sector	150	4.2667	1.26208	.10305		

Table 9.2

Table 9.2 demonstrates the perception of employees towards recruitment and selection practice in publicly owned and privately owned sector banks. Publicly owned banks have a mean value range from 4.1 to 4.3 and 3.9 to 4.3 for privately owned sector banks on different criterion which shows that employees of both sector banks are agree with the statements and significant value of t (p value) range from .091 to .584 on different parameters (5% significance level) which demonstrates that there is no noteworthy disparity between publicly owned and privately owned sector banks on recruitment and selection practice which signifies that employees perceived that their banks have transparent selection policy which show that organization values individuals which

leads to greater enthusiasm, reduced turnover and lower training costs because competent and creative applicants will execute well and accomplish organisational objectives effectively.

9.3 Promotion practice perceived by public sector and private sector banks employees:

Promotion practice	Banks	n	$\bar{x}$	Σ	$\sigma_{\bar{x}}$	t	p value
Promotion rely upon results/outcomes of employees.	Public Sector	150	3.8067	1.30408	.10648	0.861	0.390
	Private Sector	150	3.6800	1.24415	.10158		
Biasness/Partiality predominates whenever rewards are given.	Public Sector	150	2.1067	1.33183	.10874	0.461	0.645
	Private Sector	150	2.1800	1.41928	.11588		
The promotion relies upon the relationship/bonding between managers/superiors and employees.	Public Sector	150	2.3933	1.54527	.12617	1.168	0.244
	Private Sector	150	2.6133	1.71369	.13992		
When promoted, the employees are sent to another location.	Public Sector	150	3.9267	1.03039	.08413	1.186	0.237
	Private Sector	150	4.0600	.91395	.07462		
Appropriate to conclude that you are satisfied with promotion approach continued in your Bank	Public Sector	150	3.8600	1.00355	.08194	1.237	0.217
	Private Sector	150	3.7067	1.13839	.09295		

Table 9.3

Table 9.3 demonstrates the perception of employees towards promotion practice in publicly owned and privately owned sector banks. Publicly owned banks have a mean value range from 2.1 to 3.9 and 2.1 to 4.0 for privately owned sector banks on different criterion which shows that employees of both sector banks are agree with the statements and significant value of t (p value) range from .217 to .645 on different parameters (5% significance level) which demonstrates that there is no noteworthy disparity between publicly owned and privately owned sector banks on promotion strategy which signifies that employees perceived that their banks have robust promotion policy which motivates people to upgrade in order to flourish in their careers and an important strategy for personnel retention and when employees are given opportunities to advance or develop, they are more likely to stay with the organisation. This drive eventually leads to increased performance.

9.4 Employee participation practice perceived by public sector and private sector banks employees:

Employee participation practice	Banks	n	$\bar{x}$	Σ	$\sigma_{\bar{x}}$	t	p value
Importance is given to new or unique ideas of employees.	Public Sector	150	3.9333	1.04056	.08496	1.174	0.241
	Private Sector	150	3.7800	1.21440	.09916		
Bank appreciate the employees for their new or unique ideas	Public Sector	150	3.9400	.98465	.08040	.532	0.595
	Private Sector	150	4.000	.96933	.07915		
Employees themselves participate energetically in activities to achieve banking goals	Public Sector	150	3.9867	.71406	.05830	.380	0.704
	Private Sector	150	4.0133	.47750	.03899		
Bank permitted to take part in issues or matters affecting the employees	Public Sector	150	3.8400	.99718	.08142	.510	0.611
	Private Sector	150	3.7800	1.04187	.08507		

Table 9.4

Table 9.4 demonstrates the perception of employees towards employee participation practice in publicly owned and privately owned sector banks. Publicly owned banks have a mean value range from 3.8 to 3.9 and 3.7 to 4.0 for privately owned sector banks on different criterion which shows that employees of both sector banks are agree with the statements and significant value of t (p value) range from .241 to .704 on different parameters (5% significance level) which demonstrates that there is no noteworthy disparity between publicly owned and privately owned sector banks on employee participation strategy which signifies that employees perceived that their banks have fair participation policy and active empowerment at workplace enhances staff commitment and continuity, resulting in healthy working atmosphere that decreases occupational stress. Participative empowerment also leads to better unique ideas and critical thinking when challenges emerge and will settle the specific issue.

9.5 Communication practice perceived by public sector and private sector banks employees:

Communication practice	Banks	n	$\bar{x}$	Σ	$\sigma_{\bar{x}}$	t	p value
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Bank have an open-door policy for employees	Public Sector	150	3.8600	.90509	.07390	.255	0.799
	Private Sector	150	3.8333	.90796	.07413		
The work that the employees have to do is communicated to them beforehand/advance.	Public Sector	150	4.1533	.73033	.05963	1.144	0.253
	Private Sector	150	4.0467	.87728	.07163		
HR manager interact with the staff	Public Sector	150	3.7267	1.00266	.08187	1.235	0.218
	Private Sector	150	3.5733	1.14310	.09333		
Employees get the adequate detail timely to ensure that they complete their duties successfully	Public Sector	150	4.0667	.70155	.05728	.362	0.717
	Private Sector	150	4.0400	.56616	.04623		
Appropriate to conclude that you are pleased with communication process continued in your Bank	Public Sector	150	3.8667	.86441	.07058	1.724	0.086
	Private Sector	150	3.6600	1.18622	.09685		

Table 9.5

Table 9.5 demonstrates the perception of employees towards communication practice in publicly owned and privately owned sector banks. Publicly owned banks have a mean value range from 3.7 to 4.1 and 3.6 to 4.0 for privately owned sector banks on different criterion which shows that employees of both sector banks are agree with the statements and significant value of t (p value) range from .086 to .799 which is more than .050 on different parameters (5% significance level) which demonstrates that there is no noteworthy disparity between publicly owned and privately owned sector banks on communication practice which signifies that employees perceived that their banks have fair communication practice and employees are highly productive when their issues are acknowledged and handled, therefore creating a positive workplace culture via effective communication is beneficial. Individuals feel appreciated and inspired to perform, and as a result, their productivity increases.

9.6 Talent Management practice perceived by public sector and private sector banks employees:

Talent Management practice	Banks	n	$\bar{x}$	Σ	$\sigma_{\bar{x}}$	t	p value
What do you think the bank should	Public Sector	150	4.2267	.54523	.04452	-.911	0.363

invest in talent management	Private Sector	150	4.2867	.59457	.04855		
Does talent acquisition program is a primary concern for your institution	Public Sector	150	4.0533	1.10391	.09013	1.257	0.210
	Private Sector	150	3.8867	1.19021	.09718		
Does your bank have any strategy for the career growth of talented employees	Public Sector	150	4.0133	.91949	.07508	.894	0.372
	Private Sector	150	3.9133	1.01622	.08297		

Table 9.6

Table 9.6 demonstrates the perception of employees towards talent management practice in publicly owned and privately owned sector banks. Publicly owned banks have a mean value range from 4.0 to 4.2 and 3.8 to 4.2 for privately owned sector banks on different criterion which shows that employees of both sector banks are agree with the statements and significant value of t (p value) .210 to .372 on different parameters (5% significance level) which demonstrates that there is no noteworthy disparity between publicly owned and privately owned sector banks on talent management practice which signifies that employees perceived that their banks have fair talent management practice and organisation will concentrate on developing and sustaining high-quality professionals, as well as assisting the organisation in recognising the perfect individual for appropriate project opportunities brilliantly and make a productive staff who will remain with organization over the long haul.

10. Findings of the Study:

- ❖ The results reveal that 118 (79%) respondents from Publicly owned and 103 (68%) participants from privately owned sector bank are agreed with the statement and perceived that both banks have satisfactory recruitment and selection framework and there is no substantial disparity between these two banks on this criterion and null hypothesis is accepted.
- ❖ The results reveal that 96 (64%) participants from Publicly owned and 85 (57%) participants from privately owned sector bank are agreed with the statement and perceived that both banks have satisfactory promotion practice and there is no substantial disparity between these two banks on this criterion and null hypothesis is accepted.
- ❖ The results reveal that 89 (59%) participants from Publicly owned and 81 (54%) participants from privately owned sector bank are agreed with the statement and perceived that both banks have satisfactory employee participation framework and there is no substantial disparity between these two banks on this criterion and null hypothesis is accepted.

- ❖ The results reveal that 136 (91%) participants from Publicly owned and 124 (83%) participants from privately owned sector bank are agreed with the statement and perceived that both banks have satisfactory communication practice and there is no substantial disparity between these two banks on this criterion and null hypothesis is accepted.
- ❖ The results reveal that 129 (86%) participants from Publicly owned and 118 (79%) participants from privately owned sector bank are agreed with the statement and perceived that both banks have satisfactory talent management framework and there is no substantial disparity between these two banks on this criterion and null hypothesis is accepted.

11. Conclusion:

Managers should comprehend that sustainable competitive advantage will only be achieved if personnel perceptions are effectively recognized and handled. The chances of organisational effectiveness enhanced if personnel have an optimistic response toward their work which leads to greater enthusiasm, reduced turnover and lower training costs. In this study, majority of employees of both sector banks has optimistic perception towards HRM practices implemented in their banks i.e., recruitment and selection practice, talent management practice, communication practice, promotion practice, employee participation practice and there is no noteworthy disparity between publicly owned and privately owned sector bank on abovementioned HRM practices.

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